

PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE LEVEL OF INTERNATIONAL MARKETING IN FOREIGN ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES OF ENTERPRISES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8073103>

Annotation. The article discusses the main directions of the marketing activity of the enterprise based on the research of various authors. The main factors that modern enterprises in the competitive struggle should focus on in the process of functioning of the enterprise were identified. It was concluded that the main indicators of the effectiveness of marketing activities are quantitative and qualitative indicators that should be followed by marketers of enterprises to improve the efficiency of the company.

Keywords: marketing activity, competition, directions of marketing activity, criteria, evaluations, indicators of marketing activity, efficiency of the enterprise.

INTRODUCTION

The instability of the world market in ensuring sustainable and high economic growth in developed countries, as well as the complexity and instability of the external and internal environment for national enterprises, encourage manufacturing companies to develop new promising product lines, expand the domestic market and enter foreign markets. In a modern market economy, the availability of competitive products is not always enough; the theoretical and practical aspects of international marketing tools should be implemented in order to completely capture the foreign market. In the era of the rapid spread of social media, the marketing world is constantly changing, and brands need to constantly be aware of these processes. "The BMW brand sold 2.46 million vehicles worldwide in 2017 alone, but started relationships with 2,46 million customers. The brand not only provides consumers with a car, but also seeks to understand the needs of the buyer. Obviously, the activation of international marketing in the foreign economic activity of national enterprises is one of the important directions of economic development.

In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the use and improvement of the principles of international marketing in the foreign economic activity of enterprises. The Action Strategy of Uzbekistan defines tasks for "development of international economic cooperation, including by expanding ties with leading international and foreign financial institutions, continuing to pursue a well-thought-out policy of external debt, and effectively using attracted foreign investments and loans". An important aspect of international marketing is the study of the competitive potential of enterprises in foreign markets to meet the needs of consumers. National enterprises play an important role in the wide use of marketing complexes and types in foreign markets,

The fact that the role of countries in the global economy changes from year to year also affects international marketing systems. This is due to the fact that the share of developed countries in world industrial production is declining as a result of the expansion of production in developing countries. The share of such countries as the Republic of Korea, Singapore, Taiwan, Brazil, Malaysia and Indonesia in world industrial production is increasing. The rapid

development of industrial production has led to a sharp increase in the skills of the labor force in these countries.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The problems associated with increasing foreign economic relations, in particular, the competitiveness of various sectors of the national economy, are covered in the works of foreign scientists such as A.Weimerskirch, S.George, F.Kotler, M.Porter, R.Russell, B.Render, K.Haxever. Along with general issues of marketing organization at enterprises, various areas of marketing in foreign economic activity are also considered.

Theoretical foundations of private aspects of international and national marketing, problems related to doing business on the international market have been studied by such scientists as I.Ansoff, I.S.Berezin, F.Buquerel, A.Diane, A.Weissman, T.P.Danko, Dixon R. Peter.

The problems of development of foreign economic activity in Uzbekistan, including its marketing and innovation activities, were studied by such scientists as Zh.Zh.Zhalolov, D.M.Mukhitdinov, M.R.Y.Karieva, T.Akromov, Sh.J.Ergashkhodzhaeva, B.B.Berkinov, Z.D.Adylova.

In international marketing, it is important to organize production on the basis of a multifaceted, ever-growing demand on a global scale, with the simultaneous delivery of goods to different parts of the world. Such an approach, because it reflects the laws of the market, is complex and contradictory, and creates the basis for new problems. Because an increase in the number and type of goods produced increases the need for resources. In the international marketing policy of developing countries, increased competition in foreign markets, instability of exchange rates, difficulties in determining an effective pricing policy, problems of adapting products to new markets do not allow making optimal decisions [1, pp.34-36].

In international marketing, modern technologies, especially information communications, are becoming one of the influences factors⁷. As a result of the accelerated development of information and communication technologies, the world economy has become more global. Computer technology opens up new possibilities in marketing. Thanks to new capabilities, enterprises can deliver products to the buyer on the world market, regardless of where he lives.

The fact that the role of countries in the global economy changes from year to year also affects international marketing systems. This is due to the fact that the share of developed countries in world industrial production is declining as a result of the expansion of production in developing countries. The share of such countries as the Republic of Korea, Singapore, Taiwan, Brazil, Malaysia and Indonesia in world industrial production is increasing. The rapid development of industrial production has led to a sharp increase in the skills of the labor force in these countries [2, p.67].

Currently, the concept of international marketing of companies in foreign economic activity is characterized by the movement of goods and services on the world market and depends on the level of participation of the company in foreign economic activity. The participation of countries and companies in foreign economic activity can be as follows:

the country or company does not export goods on a regular basis and imports goods and services from abroad;

raw materials and modern technologies are imported or exported as a result of the active participation of a country or company in the international division of labor;

a country or a company participates in international industrial and scientific and technical cooperation in the form of joint production. This is primarily due to a number of reasons, such as

the need for cheap labor between countries, the need for countries and companies to be active in the international division of labor.

Especially, determining the reasons for entering the foreign market for companies will be the basis for a quick start of marketing work. Here, along with the possibility of entering foreign markets, it is important for the company to develop a set of marketing activities [6, p.54].

An important aspect of the concept of production in international marketing is the production system operating in the foreign market, the exporting company will be able to go abroad, adapting the production system to market requirements, improving the characteristics of the product (service), ensuring the efficiency of transport logistics. As a result of entering foreign markets, the company must increase production and volume of work several times, introduce modern technologies. Typically, this concept is used when there is a need to generate income in response to a sharp increase in demand for the company's goods in the external market or a decrease in value.

RESEARCH RESULTS

There are a large number of methods for improving the effectiveness of marketing activities, which differ from each other in terms of the principle of construction, are focused on different users and combine financial and non-financial tools and indicators. Some areas of increasing the effectiveness of marketing activities have been applied in practice. At the same time, each of the directions is characterized by various advantages, but also has certain disadvantages. However, it is obvious that the application of any methods and the implementation of directions related to changes in the marketing activities of companies cannot be implemented independently without taking into account the systemic nature of the business [11, p.294].

Evaluation of marketing activities should be aimed at the implementation of the following activities: determining the optimal solution based on the calculation of the effectiveness of the marketing activities of the enterprise at the stage of its development; calculation of the effectiveness of the marketing activities of the enterprise at the end of a given period of time, based on the actual results obtained; determination of the factors that influence the main performance indicators of the marketing activity of the enterprise, their interaction, the level of their influence on the main performance indicators; identification of reserves to improve the efficiency of the enterprise. The main indicators of the economic efficiency of marketing activities include: the volume of growth in sales of products, the provision of services for a given period; the ratio of the increase in sales of the product (provision of services) to the amount of costs for marketing activities; the ratio of the increase in profits received after the implementation of marketing activities to the amount of costs for their implementation; dynamics of the level of expenses for marketing activities in the total volume of sales (provision of services); expenses for marketing activities per thousand clients (consumers) covered by marketing activities; the ratio of the increase in the acquisition of goods (provision of services), provoked by the marketing activities of the enterprise, to the total number of purchases, etc. dynamics of the level of expenses for marketing activities in the total volume of sales (provision of services); expenses for marketing activities per thousand clients (consumers) covered by marketing activities; the ratio of the increase in the acquisition of goods (provision of services), provoked by the marketing activities of the enterprise, to the total number of purchases, etc. dynamics of the level of expenses for marketing activities in the total volume of sales (provision of services); expenses for

marketing activities per thousand clients (consumers) covered by marketing activities; the ratio of the increase in the acquisition of goods (provision of services), provoked by the marketing activities of the enterprise, to the total number of purchases, etc [3, p.86].

The main directions for improving the efficiency of marketing activities can be called a set of measures that allows you to influence, first of all, the internal factors of the marketing environment. The main focus should be on improving the organizational structure of the marketing service, introducing new technologies into the company's activities, improving the functional areas of marketing, introducing strategic planning and strategic enterprise management, as well as methods and tools for monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness and efficiency of marketing activities. The main indicators of the effectiveness of marketing activities are quantitative and qualitative indicators. Quantitative indicators include, first of all, indicators of increasing profits or reducing costs.

It should also be noted that existing approaches do not always take into account the dynamics of the external environment and do not provide dynamic balance with the external environment. This indicates the need to develop methods for changes in marketing activities, taking into account the interconnection and interdependence of measures to improve the effectiveness of marketing, the enterprise system as a whole, its internal and external environment based on the efficient use of resources.

As in all service industries, the definition of marketing strategies in the service export system is more difficult than in the field of material production. When developing marketing strategies for service providers, it is recommended that you first conduct a marketing audit to determine the types of services that are effective and profitable. This is useful for determining the direction of the entity exporting the service. The company can then deal with the allocation of the resources available to it. In this case, it is important to know in advance the directions of inefficient activity.

Once the export company's marketing activities have been determined, priorities are set. Some of the identified types of services can further add value to services. Therefore, it is recommended to determine the level of significance by the priority of types of services with the involvement of experts. In this case, one of the most optimal methods is the classification of types of services according to their degree of importance in ensuring the efficiency of the enterprise [4, p.29].

Based on communication activities that ensure the success of the marketing strategy, service providers have a tariff policy. It is the tariff policy that will allow consumers to bring the need to the level of demand and will stimulate the formation of a new market for services. Given the diversity of entities operating in the service market in terms of size, financial position and specialization, it is advisable to classify the appropriate pricing strategies for them. [10, p.358]

When studying the export potential of industrial enterprises, it is advisable to conduct a comprehensive study of the export potential of an enterprise as an element of its relative potential. In this regard, it is important to consider the export potential in the context of economic potential, aggregate and export potential based on the structural and logistical approach. However, it should be noted that the export potential is not a static process, its formation and implementation is a constantly changing, that is, a dynamic process.

Figure 1. General and export potential of the enterprise

When assessing the export potential of an enterprise as a whole, it should be borne in mind that such a potential itself consists of various elements. The components of the export potential are all material and non-material, financial and labor resources necessary for the development of the enterprise [7, p.48].

With the acceleration of scientific and technological progress, the role of technology increases not only as a factor of strategic competitive advantage, but also as a certain barrier to entry into the market. At the same time, the trend of globalization of the economy increases the priority of the technological boundaries of the market over geographical boundaries. Thus, the technology used can be considered as production, on the one hand, and as a market classifier, on the other.

On the basis of such a classification, it is possible to single out technology-oriented enterprises, specific production and market criteria that form structural features, and as a result of their proper management, a synergistic effect can be obtained in the form of a strategic competitive advantage from the export potential.

ANALYSIS

As you know, one of the main problems of marketing in today's conditions of intense competition is the problem of selling goods, so the main emphasis in the modern concept of marketing is on the product, adapting it to the desires of the consumer. In the course of the study,

modern marketing concepts and their features were studied. Today, the concept of relationship marketing is becoming more and more popular. Thus, the main goal of the research work is to coordinate the relationship between consumers, sellers and intermediaries on a beneficial basis.

The competitive environment in the market is built on the basis of the dynamics and size of the market share. This should be assessed by dividing these enterprises into different types depending on their status and level of competitiveness, as well as their ability to withstand competitive pressures. In this case, it is advisable to take into account the dynamics of the market share [9, p.161].

Studies also show that the market is strong if the growth rate is above 10% and weak if the growth rate is less than 5%. This means that market share growth rates will be above 10% for large enterprises with a competitive position, 6-10% for those improving their position, 5-6% growth for enterprises that are losing their competitiveness, and less than 5% for enterprises which are rapidly losing ground [8, p.159].

This method allows you to assess the competitiveness of the enterprise immediately by 2 indicators. The benchmark is the maximum value of competitive indicators. The method of determining the aggregate indicator of competitiveness is an effective method. To determine it, it is recommended to use the index method:

$$K = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n C_i \cdot K_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n C_i}, \text{ (one)}$$

where: K_i – competitiveness of the i-th product of the enterprise;

N- the total number of products manufactured at the enterprise;

C_i – the volume of produced type i of products;

Thus, in order to increase the competitiveness of domestic producers and further increase their export potential, the following can be noted:

strengthening the internal competitive environment for national producers, reducing the cost of goods and services through the widespread introduction of advanced science and technology;

optimization of the process of regional specialization within the country, taking into account the advantages of regional competition and the requirements of the world market;

creation of programs for the internationalization of national brands and the development of measures to create a positive image of the country's goods and services [5, p.93].

CONCLUSIONS

A reasonable organization of export-oriented production will strengthen and provide for further improvement of the company's export potential. In this regard, attention should be focused on identifying the company's ability to create new value based on a variety of products and services, actively use marketing communications, develop and further strengthen the national brand and maximize these opportunities.

In conclusion, the use of effective methods for assessing the export potential and the level of its use, the long-term strategy of the enterprise, which directly affects its current policy, and decisions related to determining the need for financial, labor and material and technical resources, developing a development plan and increasing competitiveness will basis for

improving efficiency. In this regard, it is important to introduce a mechanism for forming the export potential of an enterprise and evaluating its effectiveness.

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